

PEDAGOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF DEVELOPING PATRIOTIC SENSE OF FUTURE LAWYERS ON THE BASIS OF A SITUATIONAL APPROACH

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Ф.А.Досумходжаев

*Тошкент Давлат Юридик Университетининг Ихтисослаштирилган филиали
катта ўқитувчиси, ЎзПФИТИ мустақил изланувчиси*

F.A.Dosumhodjaev

*Senior Lecturer, Specialized Branch, Tashkent State Law University, Independent
Researcher, UzPFIT*

Ф. А. Досумходжаев

*Стрший преподаватель специализированного филиала Ташкентского
государственного юридического университета, независимый исследователь
УзПФИТИ.*

Резюме: Мақолада бўлажак ҳуқуқшуносларнинг ватанпарварлик туйғусини ривожлантиришга қаратилган педагогик тушунчалар, ватанпарварлик туйғусини ривожлантиришнинг ижтимоий-педагогик аҳамияти, жамиятдаги ўзига хос тарихий вазиятга қараб ватанпарварлик турли йўналишларга эга бўлиши, инсондаги ватанпарварлик тушунчасининг номаён бўлиш хусусиятлари баён этилган.

Таянч сўзлар: Ватан, ватанпарварлик, педагогик, маънавият, интеграл, урф-одат, қадрият, анъана, профилактик, ҳуқуқбузарлик, жамоатчилик.

Резюме: В статье описываются педагогические концепции будущих юристов, направленные на развитие чувства патриотизма, социально-педагогическая значимость воспитания чувства патриотизма, многообразие патриотизма в зависимости от конкретной исторической ситуации в обществе, невидимость понятия патриотизма в человек

Ключевые слова: Родина, патриотизм, педагогический, духовность, интеграл, традиция, ценность, традиция, профилактика, правонарушение, общественность.

Abstract: The article discusses pedagogical concepts aimed at developing a sense of patriotism in future lawyers, the socio-pedagogical significance of the development of patriotism, the diversity of patriotism depending on the specific historical situation in society, the peculiarities of the concept of patriotism in society.

Key words: Motherland, patriotism, pedagogy, spirituality, integrity, tradition, value, tradition, prevention, delinquency, community.

At a time of rapid development, special attention should be paid to the formation of a sense of patriotism of professionals in the field of crime prevention and public safety. After all, experts in the field of crime prevention and public safety must be able to ensure its honor and dignity as a member of the state, to fight for its interests. Creating sufficient knowledge and skills for crime prevention and public safety professionals to successfully perform their duties requires the establishment of an integrated pedagogical system. In the educational process, a sufficient basis is created for the comprehensive development of professionals working in the field of crime prevention and public safety of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the acquisition of professional skills. Ўзбекистон Training of personnel in the field of crime prevention and public safety in the Republic of Uzbekistan in the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2019 No PP-4166 "On additional measures to improve the system of training in the field of crime prevention and public safety" and 2017 PF-4958 No. 2 of 16 February "On further improvement of the system of postgraduate education" and other legal documents. Over the past three years, the Republic of Uzbekistan has undergone many reforms in the field of public safety. The socio-pedagogical significance of the development of a sense of patriotism is related to the long-term pedagogical activity of moral education of young people. In times of social change, previous values are usually lost, instructions requiring new spiritual and moral changes, crises in the spiritual and moral development of the individual, and cultural and behavioral patterns provoked by the disruption of the minds of young people who are alien to us.

Homeland (Arabic "Vatan" - motherland) means the place, territory, social environment, country where people live, where their descendants and ancestors were born and raised.

The concept of patriotism in the pedagogical encyclopedia (Greek patriotes - compatriot, patris - homeland) - the country of birth, love for the motherland, devotion, service to its development through their actions, devotion to the freedom and prosperity of the motherland, its borders, inviolability, independence a term denoting the social, spiritual, and moral qualities of the motherland, which signifies the devotion, knowledge, and experience, the dedication of the whole life, for the honor, glory, and happiness of the motherland.

Patriotism is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon. In the explanatory dictionary, patriotism is interpreted as "love for the motherland". According to his definition, the word "patriot" translated from the Greek "patriot" means "patriot" - "son of the fatherland". The terms "homeland" and "motherland" themselves borrow from Latin and entered the French vocabulary in the 16th century.

The essence of patriotism can be expressed in a general form, simply saying that

patriotism is devotion, glory and love for the Motherland. Patriotism is the inseparability of one's homeland, first and foremost, the inseparability of spiritual ties with it. Patriotism is active, devotion, service to the Motherland, the highest manifestation of which is protection from enemies with weapons in his hands. Patriotism, as one of the most important values of society, combines social, political, spiritual, moral, cultural, historical and other components. First of all, as an emotionally high attitude towards the Homeland, patriotism acts as one of the highest human feelings. An important component of a person's spiritual wealth, which is characterized by height, is the degree of his socialization.

True patriotism is always solidarity. It is carried out in the activities of the power and personality, which effectively stimulates the spirituality, citizenship and social activity of man. The historical foundations of the formation and development of patriotism are the system of values of a relatively closed territorial community of people, a certain way of life, special interests, which is characterized by the existence of isolated homeland. The first elements of patriotism are the addition to the natural environment of the human environment, which originated in ancient forms, the echo of which is the emotional attitude of many to the so-called homeland, the small homeland - the place where the formation of man as a person occurs. At the same time, the observance of living conditions and peculiarities is formed, the socio-cultural environment of the Motherland is determined. In general, the development of a sense of patriotism is greatly influenced by the following: the formation of feelings, ethnic (tribal, later - national) collective and religious. Their historical experience and traditions, as well as their character, the state of interethnic and interreligious relations, influence the content and forms of the manifestation of patriotism. The formation of the state is inextricably linked with the development of a sense of patriotism. A responsible attitude to the state and state power in general, the political environment becomes an integral and important part of patriotism, thereby acquiring the character of political consciousness. Depending on the specific historical situation in the society, patriotism can take different directions - from unconditional support of the existing political regime to its rejection.

The most important thing in the development of a sense of patriotism at the individual level is a stable, integral characteristic of man, in which three characteristics can be distinguished in an emphatic way.

First of all, the most important aspect of patriotism is love for the Motherland, devotion to the Motherland. It is actually a social feeling - a sense of community, unity, solidarity with the family and a sense of belonging to loved ones, their destiny. In ordinary life and in historical situations, patriotism represents a single emotional-volitional complex. It is love for the Motherland that awakens the will, the unity of lovers, requires active, energetic and in some cases sacrifice for the Motherland.

Second, patriotism, in addition to social feelings, is expressed in other personal characteristics. and traditions, knowledge of the history of the Homeland (respect for other

peoples, their customs and culture, intolerance of race and national hostility); Striving to strengthen the power of the Motherland, readiness to defend the Motherland, to promote the consistent development of the Motherland is a combination of personal and public interests.

Third, patriotism at the individual level is an integral relationship with other qualities directly formed by others (except patriotism).

The social and moral imperative that characterizes a person's attitude to the Homeland and the Homeland and its promotion is a patriotic activity. An important part of large-scale patriotism is the public consciousness, emotions, values in relation to their people, way of life, history, culture, state, system of core values, which are manifested in collective feelings.

Public consciousness, patriotism characterizes not only the most important but also as an element of the edge of society, as well as a necessary condition for its sustainable development, and at the same time patriotism serves as an important internal mobilization and a source for society development. Failure to value patriotism as the most important component of society leads to a weakening of consciousness, a slowdown in socio-economic, spiritual, social and state development. Emotions, ideas, beliefs, customs and traditions, including patriotism, are constantly influenced by all areas of life. Patriotism demonstrates the love for the Motherland, its inseparability with its history, culture, achievements and problems for a person.

Patriotism is one of the factors of development, it is a society and its vital attribute. Typically, it serves to unite different social, national, religious, and other groups, groups of citizens, which is especially evident when observed in external threats.

Patriotism in man is manifested in three directions: 1) knowledge - the acquisition of values inherent in the concept of homeland; 2) belief - the transformation of the acquired knowledge in the field of values into belief; 3) action - the expression of one's faith through practical activity. At the same time, the main components of patriotism as a public life: conscious patriotism, patriotic attitude and patriotic activity.

Conscious patriotism is a reflection of the importance of the subject, their readiness to take the necessary measures to protect the Motherland and its national interests. Clear patriotic movement, as well as the interaction of the moral and ethical regulatory subject with the object of his patriotic activity.

The practice of patriotic relations arising in the social process shows a real connection between the subject and the object of his actions, patriotism is a specific type of change of all kinds of influence on the object. Patriotic relations are a necessary condition for the materialization of patriotic consciousness and the activity of patriotic realization.

Patriotic activity is a way to embody a conscious patriotic consciousness and to exert all kinds of influence on the object of patriotism, a set of actions aimed at achieving patriotic

goals.

This activity is the material basis of the truly perceived and visible aspect of patriotism. It is based on the patriotic actions of the unity of the rational, emotional and volitional components. These actions can be considered patriotic if they are aimed at serving the Motherland, if they can express the individual's social and moral responsibility for the fate of his country. Patriotic spirituality, citizenship and social activity of the individual, any other subject of the state, understanding of its close connection with the Motherland.

Homeland, motherland, motherland - the place of birth and upbringing of a person, the social or national community of people and the country to which they belong are the necessary conditions for their well-being; historically a territory belonging to this people. By nature, the social, political and cultural environment of the people, the Homeland unites them into a single community, while at the same time separating them from others. This community is characterized by a number of characteristics over a long period of historical development: the region to which it belongs, its ethnic composition, religion, language and national cultural characteristics, and so on.

In short, the sense of homeland is not inherited in the human mind. They are formed throughout human life. Dependence on places of birth and people, a sense of love for the Homeland grows with an understanding of their connection to the country and a conscious struggle against oppressors and evils. Emotionally elevated attitude towards the Homeland, accepting it as a person of the highest social significance, reflects the values of social and individual consciousness and is strengthened by patriotism. It unites compatriots, different people in social relations and solidarity of different nations in general relations, common readiness to serve the interests of the Motherland, moral duty and commitment to protect the Motherland. Homeland is a manifestation of true patriotism, a vision of values that serves to realize one of the highest.

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